

A Picture-Based Field Guide

Shallow Coastal Communities around Gotland, Sweden

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Figure on the cover:

Schematic representation of hard- and soft bottoms in the Baltic Sea. Created by Nina Lepola.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been used for language proofreading.

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Introduction

The shallow coastal environments around Gotland: a vital link between nature and people

The island of Gotland lies in the heart of the Baltic Sea, surrounded by shallow coastal waters that are both ecologically rich and deeply connected to local culture and livelihoods. These nearshore environments, with their exposed rocky areas, as well as calm, sheltered bays, underwater meadows, and sandy seafloors, are essential to a wide range of plants, animals, and human activities. For centuries, these ecosystems have provided food, recreation, and natural beauty, and they continue to do so today.

Gotland's shallow waters are home to many fish species that are both ecologically important and valued by local communities, such as cod, pike, and perch. These fish depend on the coastal zone for feeding, breeding, and sheltering, especially during their early life stages. Vegetated areas – places where underwater plants like seagrasses and algae grow – are particularly important as nurseries where young fish can grow safely, find food, and avoid predators. These same habitats also support countless small invertebrates such as snails and tiny crustaceans, which in turn are eaten by fish and birds.

The underwater vegetation, often called Submerged Aquatic Vegetation (SAV), plays a central role in keeping the coastal ecosystem healthy. It creates a three-dimensional structure where animals can hide and forage. However, these valuable meadows face increasing pressure. In the Baltic Sea, excess nutrients from land, caused by runoff from agriculture, sewage, and other human activities, can trigger the growth of fast-growing algae that form thick mats. These mats can smother the underwater plants, but also create new habitats for some invertebrates, making the balance complex.

Gotland's coast is not only a regional hotspot for biodiversity, but it is also woven into the island's cultural and economic life. The island has a long tradition of fishing, with historic *fiskelägen* (small fishing villages) dotting the shoreline. Today, Gotland is also a popular destination for sport fishing and tourism, particularly in summer, when underwater vegetation is at its peak and fish spawning is underway.

Yet, like many coastal areas worldwide, Gotland's shallow habitats are under threat from several human activities. These include physical changes like the construction of marinas or harbours, pollution from nutrients and toxic substances, the spread of invasive species, and even indirect effects of fishing, such as damage to the seafloor. Research shows that many fish species, especially those that rely on specific habitats during their early life stages, are highly vulnerable when these environments are degraded or lost.

That is why marine scientists and policymakers have increasingly embraced the idea of Essential Fish Habitat, a concept that highlights the importance of protecting those coastal areas that are crucial for fish to feed, breed, and grow. In Gotland and across the Baltic Sea, shallow vegetated areas, lagoons, sheltered bays, and soft seabed all fall into this category. These places are not only biologically rich, but also provide the foundation for sustainable fisheries, recreation, and cultural heritage.

Preserving and restoring these habitats around Gotland is not just about protecting nature for its own sake; it is about safeguarding the ecological and cultural wealth that supports both people and wildlife, now and for the future.

The distribution of marine organisms (including bacteria, algae, plants, animals, and others) depends on many factors, such as salinity, oxygen levels, depth, and light availability. The type of substrate (the surface where the organisms live) is one of the most important and easily visible of these factors. Seafloor substrates are divided into hard (bedrock, boulders, stones) and soft (gravel, sand, mud, silt) bottoms.

Species have different requirements for living, and are more or less successful at colonising different areas. In Figure 1, you can see how various species take space in different types of bottoms and at different depths in the Baltic Sea.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of hard- and soft bottoms in the Baltic Sea. Created by Nina Lepola.

Pictures were taken around Gotland (Lergrav, Valleviken, Visby (Kallis), and Gustavsvik), unless otherwise indicated.

Here is an overview of the **main groups of organisms** – algae, plants, and animals – that you are likely to see.

Group	Examples	What to look for
Algae	Green algae, brown algae, red algae	Leafy fronds, bushy tufts, filamentous mats on rocks, or drifting
Vascular plants	Seagrass, pondweeds, and water milfoil	Grass-like shoots, rooted plants in sand or mud, dense meadows
Cnidaria	Jellyfish (Scyphozoa)	Pulsating jellyfish in open water, often drifting near the surface
Ctenophora	Comb jellies	Translucent, gelatinous spheres, shimmering rainbow bands
Mollusca	Snails (Gastropoda), clams, and mussels (Bivalvia)	Coiled shells on rocks and plants, mussel beds, buried clams
Arthropoda (Crustacea)	Amphipods, isopods, crabs, shrimps	Small shrimplike animals among vegetation, crabs on the seabed
Bryozoa	Colonial bryozoans	Tiny, lacy, or encrusting colonies on seagrass, algae, and rocks
Chordata (Fish)	Stickleback, gobies, and flatfish	Small fish darting in seagrass, resting on sand or mud

Underwater Vegetation/Submerged Aquatic Vegetation (SAV)

Along Gotland's coasts, beneath the surface of sheltered bays and shallow waters, lies a rich world of underwater vegetation. Known collectively as Submerged Aquatic Vegetation (or SAV), these underwater meadows include both aquatic plants and algae. Although often invisible from the shore, these habitats are essential for supporting coastal life, including the fish, invertebrates, and birds that people have depended on for generations.

SAV creates shelter and food for many species. Its leaves and stems provide safe places for young fish to hide from predators, and its surfaces offer attachment points for small animals and microscopic life. By slowing water movement, SAV also helps fine sediments settle, which improves water clarity. In fact, these underwater plants and algae act much like coastal forests or grasslands, shaping the seascape, influencing water quality, and creating homes for wildlife.

Around Gotland, SAV supports diverse communities of small invertebrates, such as snails, crustaceans (like isopods and amphipods), and insect larvae. These animals, in turn, feed fish and waterbirds and help transfer energy up the food chain. Grazing invertebrates also help keep the vegetation healthy by eating tiny algae that could otherwise smother plant leaves.

However, like many coastal areas in the Baltic Sea, Gotland's SAV faces growing pressure from human activities, especially nutrient pollution (runoff from agriculture and sewage) that causes excess algal growth. This can smother underwater plants and change the balance of life below the surface. Understanding the role of both algae and plants is key to protecting these vital habitats.

To better explore this world, we now turn to the two main types of underwater vegetation: algae and plants.

Algae: The Flexible Architects of the Seafloor

Algae are a diverse group of aquatic organisms that range from microscopic species to large seaweeds. In Gotland's coastal waters, macroalgae (the larger, visible forms) play a significant role in shaping underwater habitats. Unlike flowering (or higher) plants, algae do not have roots, stems, or leaves, but they can still form complex structures that provide food and shelter.

One key feature of algae is their ability to grow in many forms and places. They can attach to rocks, other plants, or the seafloor. They can also break loose and form drifting mats that float with currents and winds. Around Gotland, common algae in these mats include green algae like *Cladophora* and *Chaetomorpha*, brown algae like *Pilayella* and *Ectocarpus*, and red algae such as *Ceramium*. Sometimes, mats also include filamentous cyanobacteria like *Aphanizomenon* and *Nodularia*.

These drifting mats are a double-edged sword. On the one hand, they can create temporary new habitats and food for small animals, adding to the diversity of coastal life. On the other hand, when nutrient levels are high, as they have been across the Baltic Sea since the 1970s, these mats can grow excessively. Thick, long-lasting mats can block sunlight, reduce oxygen levels, and smother both plants and the seafloor. This can reduce the variety and abundance of small animals and ultimately harm fish populations that rely on more stable, rooted habitats.

Studies have shown that the animals living in algal mats differ from those found in underwater plant beds. While both habitats can support life, the epifaunal communities (animals living on vegetation) tend to be richer and more stable in plant-dominated areas. As nutrient pollution and warming waters continue to change the Baltic Sea, understanding how drifting algae affect coastal ecosystems is more important than ever.

Look for:

- Tidal pools, rocky shorelines, and sheltered bays for dense clusters of seaweeds
- Floating mats or dense underwater meadows of algae, especially in calm, nutrient-rich waters
- Seasonal blooms in early spring or late summer, particularly with green algae (e.g., *Chaetomorpha*)
- When submerged, algae may sway gently with the current, providing shelter for small fish and invertebrates

***Cladophora glomerata* (Linnaeus) Kützing, 1843**

English: Cladophora

Swedish: Grönslick

Cladophora glomerata (Fig. 2) is a branched, filamentous alga. Juveniles of many animals, especially small crustaceans, are often found within its filaments. It forms the green alga belt in the shallowest areas, where it is strongly attached to the substrate.

Figure 2. *Cladophora* grows on shallow water hard bottoms (boulders and bedrock). Many small animals can be found between its filaments, which are eaten by fish and other animals – such as the two ducks in the picture. Photo by Chiara D'Agata.

***Fucus vesiculosus* Linnaeus, 1753**

English: Bladder wrack

Swedish: Blåstång

Fucus vesiculosus (Fig. 3) is a large brown alga. It often has round air bladders (hence the common name), but they can also be missing or very poorly developed. It can live for several decades, given the right conditions. It is one of the main species forming the brown alga belt. *Fucus vesiculosus* is a key species in the Baltic Sea. With its canopy, it slows water movement, reducing mechanical stress to other organisms, and providing a sturdy, three-dimensional substrate for other animals and algae to live. For these reasons, this seaweed is called a “keystone species”. It is the only large species that can grow on rocky seafloors in this part of the Baltic Sea. The function of dense *Fucus* belts in the Baltic has been compared to that of underwater forests.

Figure 3. Bladder wrack (*Fucus vesiculosus*) from the west coast of Gotland. Note the gas bladders and the presence of small marine snails and other algae living on it. Photos by Chiara D'Agata and Lina M. Nordlund.

***Furcellaria lumbricalis* (Hudson) J. V. Lamouroux, 1813**

English: Clawed fork weed

Swedish: Kräkel

Furcellaria lumbricalis is typically red/purple when growing in shaded areas, getting more golden/green in more direct sunlight. It is often found with *Fucus*.

Figure 4. Stranded *Furcellaria lumbricalis* with a blue mussel (*Mytilus edulis*) still attached. Photo by Chiara D'Agata.

***Vertebrata fucoides* (Hudson) Kuntze, 1891**

English: Black siphon weed

Swedish: Fjäderslick

Vertebrata fucoides is a common red alga (and very striking under the microscope!):

<https://www.havet.nu/livet/art/fjaderslick>

***Ceramium* sp. Roth, 1797**

English: Ceramium

Swedish: Ullsläke

The most common species in the Baltic Sea are *C. tenuicorne* and *C. virgatum*.

Figure 5. *Ceramium* growing on stones. Note the striped colour pattern. Photo by Chiara D'Agata.

***Chara* sp. Linnaeus, 1753**

English: Stoneworth

Swedish: Sträfsse

Stoneworts are green algae. However, their structure is that of vascular (= true) plants. The part above the sediment is composed of a central stem, from which branches are arranged in regular whorls. Small, colourless rhizoids, which can resemble fine roots, anchor the stonewort in muddy or sandy sediments.

Figure 6. The stoneworth *Chara*. Photo by Chiara D'Agata.

Aquatic Plants: The Anchored Foundations of Coastal Life

In contrast to algae, aquatic plants are more closely related to land plants. They have roots, stems, and leaves, and they anchor firmly into soft sediments. Around Gotland, these plants form underwater meadows that offer some of the most stable and productive habitats in the coastal zone.

Common plants in Gotland's shallow waters include pondweeds (*Potamogeton* and *Stuckenia* species), water milfoils (*Myriophyllum* species), and, less frequently, eelgrass (*Zostera marina*). Eelgrass, well-known from saltier waters, is rarer here because it struggles in the lower salinity of the central Baltic Sea. Instead, pondweeds and milfoils often dominate. These rooted plants provide a three-dimensional habitat. Their leaves and stems offer surface area for small animals to cling to and graze, while their roots stabilise sediments and improve water clarity. Studies show that areas with dense plant cover, complex leaf shapes, and taller vegetation support more diverse and abundant invertebrate communities. Amphipods, isopods, snails, and insect larvae are especially common.

These small animals are vital food for fish, particularly young pike, perch, and other species important to Gotland's fishers and sport anglers. They also help maintain the balance of life in the vegetation by grazing on tiny algae, keeping plant leaves clean and productive. Compared to bare sand or drifting algal mats, plant meadows consistently support more species and higher biomass of invertebrates. This makes them essential not only for biodiversity, but also for sustaining fish populations and maintaining healthy coastal waters.

Look for:

- Eelgrass (*Zostera marina*): Long, ribbon-like, bright green leaves (30–60 cm) growing in underwater meadows; leaves sway gently in the current
- Horned pondweed: Fine, thread-like leaves in bushy tufts; fruits (small, horned seeds) may be visible
- Fennel pondweed: Long, slender, branching stems with delicate leaves; often mixed with other plants in shallow bays
- Shore weed: Short, grass-like rosettes found in the transition between land and water
- Reed beds: Tall (up to 2–3 m) grass with feathery flower heads along the shoreline, especially in lagoons and sheltered bays
- Look for dense, grassy underwater beds where fish and snails hide
- Calm bays, lagoons, and areas behind sandbars or reefs are hotspots for these plants
- In early summer, you may spot tiny flowers or seed structures on pondweeds and eelgrass

***Myriophyllum spicatum* L.**

English: Eurasian watermilfoil

Swedish: Axslinga

The Eurasian milfoil is one of the most commonly encountered aquatic plants around Gotland. It is found on sandy-muddy bottoms, often in patches with Sago pondweed (*Stuckenia pectinata*). The stem can be light green, yellowish, or – as in this figure – reddish. The feathery leaves are arranged in whorls, often used by animals for support.

Figure 7. Eurasian watermilfoil (*Myriophyllum spicatum*) with two wandering pond snails (*Ampullaceana balthica*). Photo by Chiara D'Agata.

***Stuckenia pectinata* (L.) Börner, 1912**

English: Sago pondweed

Swedish: Borstnate

The Sago pondweed is one of the most common aquatic plants in the Baltic Proper. Around Gotland, it can form extensive patches in sheltered bays. It can reach heights of over 1.5 m.

Figure 8. New Sago pondweed growth (*Stuckenia pectinata*) with a wandering pond snail (*Ampullaceana balthica*). Photo by Chiara D'Agata.

Figure 9. Inflorescences of Sago pondweed (*Stuckenia pectinata*). Note the drifting filamentous algae that got entangled. Photo by Chiara D'Agata.

***Zostera marina* Linnaeus, 1753**

English: Eelgrass

Swedish: Ålgräs

Around Gotland, eelgrass is usually found in water deeper than 1.5 m. The blades of eelgrass have a characteristic flat and elongated shape, and a bright green colour. Eelgrass is a marine plant, which means that it is adapted to live in waters with higher salinities. Around Gotland, the salinity (generally between 5.0 and 7.5) is still within the tolerance limits of eelgrass. As the salinity of the Baltic Sea decreases moving northwards, eelgrass becomes progressively less common. It is seldom encountered north of the Archipelago Sea and is absent in the Bothnian Bay.

Figure 10. Eelgrass (*Zostera marina*) grows typically between 1 and 3 m depth around Gotland and can easily exceed 0.5 m in length. Photo by Chiara D'Agata.

Cnidaria – Jellyfish

Jellyfish are some of the most recognisable and fascinating creatures of our seascapes.

Belonging to the group Cnidaria, and more specifically to the class Scyphozoa, jellyfish are soft-bodied animals that drift through the water with a graceful, pulsing motion. Their bodies are made mostly of water, giving them a translucent, gelatinous appearance.

The familiar “bell” shape is often accompanied by long trailing tentacles, which they use both for movement and for capturing prey. These tentacles contain specialised stinging cells (called cnidocytes) that release tiny harpoon-like structures to catch plankton or small fish. Most jellyfish in coastal waters are harmless to humans, though their stings can sometimes cause mild irritation.

In shallow coastal areas, you may spot jellyfish slowly floating near the surface or gently moving with the currents. Their delicate beauty and otherworldly forms make them a striking part of the underwater scene.

Look for:

- Translucent, umbrella-shaped bell gently pulsing through the water
- Long, fine tentacles trailing beneath the bell
- Often drifting near the surface or moving slowly with currents
- Look for bluish, pinkish, or whitish hues, depending on the species
- Common species may appear in late spring to summer, often in calm, warm shallows

Figure 11: Stranded and in-between seagrass drifting moon jellies around Gotland, central Baltic Sea. Photos by Adam Fasth and Lina M. Nordlund.

***Aurelia aurita* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

English: Moon jelly

Swedish: Öronmanet

Moon jellies occur in most parts of the Baltic – from the Danish straits in the west to the Bothnian Sea in the northeast. In the central Baltic Sea, *Aurelia aurita* usually grows up to 15 centimeters in diameter.

Figure 12. Moon jelly (*Aurelia aurita*). Photo by Chiara D'Agata.

Bryozoans (Ectoprocta)

Bryozoans, often called “moss animals”, are tiny colonial invertebrates that live in both marine and freshwater environments. Each colony is made up of numerous microscopic individuals called zooids, which work together as a single organism. These colonies often form encrusting sheets, delicate lace-like networks, or branching structures that grow on rocks, shells, algae, and other submerged surfaces. Although the individual zooids are tiny and nearly invisible to the naked eye, the colonies they build can be quite noticeable and sometimes feel rough or slightly spongy to the touch.

Bryozoans filter-feed by extending a crown of tiny tentacles (called a lophophore) to capture plankton and organic particles from the water. They are important for water filtration and also provide habitat complexity, offering shelter to small invertebrates and, in the case of erect species, juvenile fish.

Look for:

- Thin, encrusting mats or branching, bushy colonies on rocks, algae, or shells
- Colonies may appear whitish, yellowish, or light brown
- Texture often rough, lacy, or slightly spongy to the touch
- Commonly seen attached to hard surfaces in shallow waters
- Best spotted by looking closely at stones or shells; colonies often cover surfaces like a fine mesh

Figure 13: Brown alga with moss animals (bryozoans). Photo by Björn S. (<https://www.flickr.com/photos/40948266@N04/>).

***Einhornia crustulenta* (Pallas, 1766)**

English: Sea mat

Swedish: Tångbark

Einhornia crustulenta is a species of Bryozoa – “moss animals”. What we see is a colony of individuals, called zooids, living enclosed in small hard “cells”. They are filter feeders; they extract food particles from the water by moving it through specialised feeding structures. The colony can be many centimetres long and wide:

<https://www.havet.nu/livet/art/tangbark>

Crustaceans (Phylum Arthropoda, Subphylum Crustacea)

Crustaceans are a diverse group of animals that include crabs, shrimps, lobsters, amphipods, isopods, and barnacles. In coastal underwater habitats like those around Gotland, the most commonly encountered crustaceans are the small, shrimp-like amphipods, the flattened isopods, and various barnacles attached to rocks and submerged vegetation.

All crustaceans share a few key features: they have jointed legs, a hard exoskeleton (which they shed as they grow), and segmented bodies. Most are excellent swimmers or crawlers, and they play crucial ecological roles as grazers, scavengers, and prey for larger animals. Crustaceans are often found hiding among algae, seagrass, or under stones, and they help keep the underwater environment clean by feeding on detritus and algae.

Look for:

- Amphipods: shrimp-like, laterally flattened, often hopping or darting among algae and seagrass
- Isopods: more flattened top-to-bottom, resembling tiny woodlice crawling on plants or rocks
- Barnacles: small, volcano-like shells attached to rocks or hard surfaces
- Hard exoskeletons and jointed legs may be visible if looking closely at small animals in hand nets
- Found clinging to submerged plants, crawling on stones, or swimming in the water column

***Amphibalanus improvisus* (Darwin, 1854)**

English: Barnacle

Swedish: Havstulipan

These sessile (= attached) animals are suspension feeders; they capture small particles and plankton from the water by extending their feather-like appendages into the water and directing them towards their mouth. Figure 14 shows a feeding barnacle on a *Fucus*. The barnacle is usually less than 15 mm in diameter.

Figure 14. A barnacle, *Amphibalanus improvisus*, feeding on *Fucus vesiculosus*. Photo by Chiara D'Agata.

***Idotea* sp. Fabricius, 1798**

English: Isopod

Swedish: Tånggrasugga

Idotea (Fig. 15) live on algae and plants and are, together with *Gammarus*, the most important Baltic grazers, feeding on filamentous algae and *Fucus*. Other than that, they have the potential to feed on a large number of different food items, including other crustaceans. This isopod is usually less than 4 centimetres long. They are “back-to-belly” compressed.

Figure 15. *Idotea bathica* on European millfoil (*Myriophyllum spicatum*). Photo by Chiara D'Agata.

***Gammarus* spp. Fabricius, 1775**

English: Amphipod

Swedish: Tångmärla

Gammarus (Fig. 16) is another key crustacean in the Baltic. Similar to *Idotea*, they live on plants and algae, where they are important grazers, especially of filamentous algae, but can feed on a variety of other food items. *Gammarus* species are, around Gotland, usually less than 2 centimetres long. They are “side-to-side” compressed.

Figure 16. View of a *Gammarus* grazing on filamentous algae. Photos by Chiara D'Agata.

Molluscs — Snails and Bivalves Beneath the Surface

Molluscs are soft-bodied animals, many of which protect themselves with a hard shell. In shallow coastal waters and seagrass beds, two main groups of molluscs stand out: **snails** (gastropods) and **bivalves** (clams and mussels). Both play important roles in the ecosystem and are surprisingly easy to spot if you know what to look for.

Snails (Gastropoda)

Snails are the grazers of the underwater world. They move slowly across rocks, algae, and seagrass leaves, feeding on microscopic algae, detritus, and biofilm. You will recognise them by their coiled shells, which range from smooth and glossy to rough and sculptured.

- **Where to look:** On seagrass leaves, among algae, or on rocks and shells. Some species are tiny (a few millimetres), while others reach several centimetres.
- **Common species:** *Theodoxus fluviatilis* (striped nerite), pondsnails, mudsnails.
- **Why they matter:** Snails help control algae growth and are an important food source for fish, birds, and crabs.

Clams and mussels (Bivalvia)

Bivalves have two hinged shells and are often buried in sediment or attached to rocks and hard surfaces. Unlike snails, they do not crawl much; instead, they filter tiny food particles from the water.

- **Where to look:** Mussels attach to rocks or seagrass roots in dense clumps; small clams bury just beneath the sand or mud. Look for tiny siphons poking out of the sediment.
- **Common species:** *Mytilus edulis* (*trossulus*) (blue mussel), Cardiidae (cockles), *Macoma balthica* (Baltic clam).
- **Why they matter:** Bivalves filter large volumes of water, helping keep it clear. Their shells provide habitat for other small animals, and they are a key food for birds, fish, and crabs.

***Ampullaceana balthica* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

English: Wandering pond snail

Swedish: Oval dammsnäcka

Figure 17. A wandering pond snail (*Ampullaceana balthica*) on a mat of cyanobacteria. Photo by Chiara D'Agata.

Hydrobiidae W. Stimpson, 1865

English: Mudsnail

Swedish: Tusensnäcka

There are several species of Hydrobiidae living in the Baltic Sea. They can be very difficult to distinguish based on morphological characteristics; therefore, we will focus on their larger family. They feed on a variety of food items: diatoms and other microalgae, bacteria, and dead plants and animals. They are minute in size (typically less than 1 centimetre).

Figure 18. An empty shell of a mudsnail, as seen under the microscope. Usually, they measure about 5 mm. The green blob is the cyanobacteria *Rivularia atra* Roth ex Bornet & Flahault, 1886. Photo by Chiara D'Agata.

***Potamopyrgus antipodarum* (J. E. Gray, 1843)**

English: New Zealand mudsnail

Swedish: Nyzeeländsk tusensnäcka

This gastropod was introduced into the Baltic Sea at the end of the 1800s through ballast waters. It is an invasive species, meaning that it spreads rapidly and can outcompete native species. Its shape is similar to other mudsnails (Hydrobiidae). The distinguishing characteristic (not always present) is a dark keel running along the whorls (as in the specimen in the picture). Most commonly found with a shell length of 3–4 mm.

Figure 19. A New Zealand mudsnail (*Potamopyrgus antipodarum*) – an introduced (= non-indigenous) species. Photo by Chiara D'Agata.

***Theodoxus fluviatilis* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

English: River nerite

Swedish: Båtsnäcka

Theodoxus fluviatilis is found in the brackish Baltic Sea, but also in freshwater. It feeds on microscopic algae, macroalgae, and plants. The size of these snails is, as most other invertebrates in this part of the Baltic Sea, small: the shell width is usually 6–7 mm in width and about 4–5 mm in height.

Figure 20. A river nerite (*Theodoxus fluviatilis*) on a rock. The species' shell whorl can be nicely seen. Photo by Chiara D'Agata.

***Mytilus edulis* Linnaeus, 1758**

English: Blue mussel

Swedish: Blåmussla

In the Baltic Sea, there are two species of blue mussels: *Mytilus edulis* and *M. trossulus*. The two are very similar and have also reproduced to form hybrids. Since it is very difficult to distinguish these species based on morphological characteristics, they are categorised under a “species complex”, and referred to commonly only as “*Mytilus edulis*”. They are filter feeders, capturing plankton from the water. They are also a keystone species, providing hard structures for other organisms to live on, food for other animals, and playing an important role in nutrient cycling. Around Gotland, *Mytilus* can grow up to 5 centimetres.

Figure 21. Stranded *Mytilus edulis* still attached to the red algae *Furcellaria lumbricalis*. Photo by Chiara D’Agata.

Cerastoderma/Parvicardium

English: Cockle

Swedish: Hjärtmussla

There are two common types of cockles around Gotland: *Cerastoderma* and *Parvicardium*. They are very similar morphologically and can be difficult to correctly distinguish from one another. These bivalves are small and reach a size of about 1 cm (shell width). Juveniles can be found in high numbers, even hundreds, in vegetated patches.

Figure 22. A cockle, *Cerastoderma/Parvicardium*, seen under the microscope. The three green blobs are the cyanobacteria *Rivularia atra*. Photo by Chiara D'Agata.

Fish (Phylum Chordata, Subphylum Vertebrata)

Fish are a familiar sight in Gotland's shallow coastal waters and bays, where both adult fish and juveniles make use of underwater vegetation like seagrass, pondweeds, and algal mats for shelter, feeding, and breeding. Barren sandy seafloors are also used by juvenile flatfishes and gobies. Fish are part of the phylum Chordata, defined by having a spinal cord, but here we focus on bony fish (Class Actinopterygii), which dominate these coastal habitats.

The fish community in Gotland's coastal waters reflects the brackish conditions of the Baltic Sea. You will encounter a mixture of species that tolerate both freshwater and marine influences. Some species are small and resident all year, while others migrate seasonally to breed or feed.

Common species include the three-spined stickleback (*Gasterosteus aculeatus*), pipefish (*Syngnathus typhle*), perch (*Perca fluviatilis*), roach (*Rutilus rutilus*), rudd (*Scardinius erythrophthalmus*), and pike (*Esox lucius*). Sticklebacks and pipefish often weave between plant stems, while larger predators like perch and pike hunt in the same vegetation zones. Baltic herring (*Clupea harengus*) and other schooling fish may occasionally appear in deeper coastal waters.

Look for:

- Three-spined stickleback: small (4–6 cm), silvery fish often close to vegetation
- Pipefish: long, thin, and stiff-bodied fish resembling plant stems
- Perch: easily recognised by dark vertical stripes and orange-tinted fins; juveniles and adults alike hide in vegetation
- Roach and rudd: medium-sized fish (15–30 cm) with silver bodies and reddish fins, often cruising in small groups
- Pike: long-bodied predator with a flat snout, well-camouflaged and lurking motionless among reeds or seagrass
- European eel (rare but possible): long, snake-like fish that may be found under rocks or in dense vegetation
- Look for darting movements in shallow water, or fish staying still among plant stems
- Calm, sunny days with clear water improve chances of seeing larger fish
- Wading slowly, snorkelling, or lifting algae carefully can reveal hidden fish

***Gasterosteus aculeatus* Linnaeus, 1758**

English: Three-spined stickleback

Swedish: Storspigg

The three-spined stickleback, named after its three sharp spines on the back, has become one of the most common fish in the coastal zone. Sticklebacks can be seen alone (especially during breeding season) or in schools. During breeding season, males develop a bright red colouration on the throat and – sometimes – a deep blue colour on the belly. The males take care of most of the parental duties: they build the nest, defend it from predators, and make sure there is always a good circulation of water around it, which maintains good oxygen levels for the developing eggs and juveniles.

Figure 23. A three-spined stickleback (*Gasterosteus aculeatus*) near a patch of Sago pondweed (*Stuckenia pectinata*). Photos by Chiara D'Agata and JaySo83 – Own work, CC BY-SA 3.0 (<https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=12601932>).

***Syngnathus typhle* Linnaeus, 1758**

English: Broad-nosed pipefish

Swedish: Tångsnälla

Figure 24. A broad-nosed pipefish (*Syngnathus typhle*) emerging from a mat of filamentous algae. Their max. length is 35 cm, but most often, *S. typhle* are around 20 cm in size. Photo by Chiara D'Agata.

***Perca fluviatilis* Linnaeus, 1758**

English: European perch

Swedish: Abborre

Figure 25: European perch specimens in a fishing net and *Fucus* habitat around Gotland. Photos by Samuel Bluth and Lina Mtwana Nordlund.

***Salmo trutta* Linnaeus, 1758**

English: Brown trout

Swedish: Öring, Havsöring

Figure 26. Carefully handled brown trout in Gotlandic coastal waters. Photo by Samuel Bluth.

Figure 27. Aquascope Underwater Window at the Gotland coast in action. Photo by Lina M. Nordlund.